

The Manifestations of Administrative Creativity in Leadership Performance of PTUK

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The study aimed to investigate the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the Technical University of Palestine in the presence of the Ramallah branch from the viewpoint of university employees, and to achieve this goal the descriptive approach was used as the most appropriate for that, the study community of all employees at Palestine Technical University was attending the Ramallah branch. 100) employee, and the study was applied to a random stratified sample of (50%); the results of the study indicated that the aspects of administrative creativity in the performance of the Palestine Technical University management were my presence in the Ramallah branch from the viewpoint of university employees was largely available, and also indicated that there are no differences Statistical function due to the variables of D. Head: the type, the academic qualification, and the number of years of experience; the recommendations of the study emphasized the importance of the administration proposing the largest possible number of new ideas to develop administrative performance and develop the professional growth of employees and the need to rely more on teamwork in problem solving by searching for new alternatives to solve problems Instead of the usual solutions.

Key words: Creativity, Administrative Creativity, Palestine Technical University, Khadoury, Ramallah

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INTRODUCTION

The continuation of scientific progress and technical development achieved in various fields is an incentive to look at things of various types in a renewed way (Drucker, P, 1985), including generating new ideas and encouraging creativity in solving the problems facing institutions at the present time (Torrington, Derek, Laura, Hall & Steven Taylor, 2008), especially in countries that strive to catch up with scientific progress and technical development (Bhutto, T. A., Farooq, R., Talwar, S., Awan, U., &Dhir, A, 2021). Therefore, some emphasize that the twenty-first century, with its progress and development in all fields (Armstrong, Michael, 2006), has made resorting to creativity an inevitable matter for countries, organizations and businessmen(Mullen, C. A. 2020).

With the advent of the third millennium, the subject of administrative creativity has gained the attention of many management writers and researchers, as the foundations for the success of business organization management began to transform into a "competitive advantage" that depends primarily on the ability of the organization and its employees to excel (Mehmood, M. S., Jian, Z., Akram, U., & Tariq, A. 2021), innovate, create and renew, which necessitates the need for the management of these organizations to develop their administrative concepts and methods to prepare the conditions for human minds to innovate and renew continuously (Ribeiro, N., Duarte, A. P., Filipe, R., & Torres de Oliveira, R. 2020), by providing an appropriate organizational climate and an interactive environment that contributes to linking and transferring the cumulative knowledge and experiences acquired, which helps to develop creativity and develop and grow the organization as an interactive entity (Pakpahan, B. A., Ariawan, S., Naibaho, D., Napitupulu, T. M., Simanjuntak, H., &Manalu, P. J. H. 2021)

The fields of creativity are many and range from solving problems using well-known methods in the field of specialization, to introducing minor improvements to an existing system (Ali, A., Wang, H., & Johnson, R. E. 2020), to introducing fundamental improvements that lead to solutions to some contradictions, to a rare scientific discovery or the invention of a new system that differs from previous systems(Pakpahan, B. A., Ariawan, S., Naibaho, D., Napitupulu, T. M., Simanjuntak, H., &Manalu, P. J. H. 2021).

Hence, innovation has become the essence of administrative creativity for any organization. Management scholars agree that contemporary organizations live in changing and complex circumstances, which makes their need for creativity an urgent need (Sijabat, E. A. S., Nimran, U., Utami, H. N., &Prasetya, A. 2021), as managers must be keen

to develop and enhance the capabilities of employees to contribute to solving problems, participate in decision-making, generate new ideas and work in the spirit of a distinguished and serious team, in order to achieve creativity in work and increase production (Renzulli, J. 2021).

Therefore, the creative leader is superior to the successful leader, as the latter leader is concerned with implementing the organization's goals, performing his duties accurately, honestly and quickly, and achieving the required results (Asbari, M. 2021).

However, the creative or innovative leader is the one who is concerned with developing the organization, creating new goals for it or developing its means and methods (Tuan, L. T. 2020), and his thinking is characterized by originality, fluency and flexibility, so he does not deal with traditional methods, but rather creates unprecedented methods (Asif, M., Miao, Q., Jameel, A., Manzoor, F., & Hussain, A. 2022).

Creativity is a type of change and renewal in the work style and its use in ways and techniques that keep pace with the requirements of the environment and the modern era, so that it seeks to meet the renewed needs of society (Lee, A., Legood, A., Hughes, D., Tian, A. W., Newman, A., & Knight, C. 2020).

Creativity is also one of the most important components of successful and distinguished institutions in their performance and achievement (Zeb, A., Abdullah, N. H., Hussain, A., & Safi, A. 2020), which seek to bring about a qualitative shift and fundamental changes in their administrative work methods, support the individuals working in them and encourage their creative behavior, so that they become more efficient and effective (Dabić, M., Stojčić, N., Simić, M., Potocan, V., Slavković, M., & Nedelko, Z. 2021).

GAPS IN THE LITERATURE

Creativity is essential for survival in a constantly changing modern world. It is the pioneer of innovation, which is essential for the development of human society; therefore, creative work is of utmost importance, as creativity has economic, social and cultural importance that is directly reflected on institutions and the society to which it belongs, and educational literature has not covered the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University Khadouri, which is what this study aims to achieve.

THE ORIGINALITY OF THE PRESENT STUDY

The emergence of technical education as an independent track within the educational tracks has demonstrated the need for categories of managers with creative administrative capabilities. Therefore, the study problem is limited to trying to identify the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch, and the reflection of this on the university's outputs in general, and the obstacles that stand in their way in including manifestations of creativity in their performance.

AIM OF THE STUDY

The research seeks to achieve a main objective, which is to enhance the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch, and to achieve the following sub-objectives:

1. Identify the reality of the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch.
2. Propose a set of procedures that would contribute to enhancing the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The Main Question: What are the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch from the point of view of the university employees?

Based on the main question the following sub-question formed:

Is there a difference in manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch due to gender, Academic degree, and years of experience?

STUDY HYPOTHESIS:

1. There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch due to gender.
2. There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch due to Academic degree.
3. There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch due to years of experience.

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

The importance of the study appears in focusing on administrative creativity, which contemporary organizations rely on as a basic resource to achieve competitive advantage; Moreover, The current study may benefit researchers in the field of administrative creativity in other institutions.

DEFINITION OF TERMS:

ADMINISTRATIVE CREATIVITY: IS THE ABILITY TO CHANGE, INNOVATE AND CREATE A NEW APPROACH OR WORK STYLE THAT IS COMPATIBLE WITH THE SURROUNDING ENVIRONMENT AND CONTRIBUTES TO MEETING THE NEEDS OF SOCIETY, AND USING THESE METHODS TO ACHIEVE THE ORGANIZATION'S GOALS EFFECTIVELY AND EFFICIENTLY.

THE RESEARCHER DEFINES IT PROCEDURALLY AS THE ABILITY OF MANAGEMENT TO SOLVE PROBLEMS IN INNOVATIVE WAYS AND CREATE NEW WORK METHODS AND DISSEMINATE THEM AMONG EMPLOYEES.

METHODS (DESIGN OF THE STUDY)

The current study adopted the descriptive analytical approach. After collecting the data, the researchers used the analytical-statistical method to answer the question of the study and interpreted the results.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE OF THE STUDY**Population of the study:**

The population of the study consisted of all all employees of Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, numbering (100) male and female employees.

Sample of the Study:

From this population a (50) sample of employees from a random cluster were chosen to respond to the questionnaire.

Table (1)

statistical description of the research sample according to demographic variables

<i>Demographic Variables</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	
<i>Gender</i>	<i>Male</i>	25
	<i>Female</i>	25
	Total	50
<i>Academic qualification</i>	<i>Bachelor</i>	27
	<i>Master</i>	15
	<i>PhD</i>	8
<i>Years of experience</i>	Total	50
	<i>Less than 5 years</i>	2
	<i>5-10 years</i>	15
	<i>More than 10 years</i>	33
	Total	50

INSTRUMENTS OF THE STUDY

The researcher developed Questionnaire to examine the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, Ramallah Branch, it consists of two sections. The first section included personal information about the respondents. The second section included (19) items, to investigate the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, Ramallah Branch, The researcher developed the questionnaire with 3-point Likert scales ranging from strongly agree - strongly disagree. The questionnaires distributed to (50) employees.

VALIDITY OF INSTRUMENTS

To ensure that the content of the questionnaire was valid, it handed to a jury of professional doctors in the field at Palestine technical university, The Panel of judges asked to evaluate the opportunities of the instrument to the whole purpose of the study. They accepted the items and the parts of the questionnaire, but they asked the researchers to follow some modifications. The researchers took these recommendations into amount before issuing the final draft of the tool, and then the instrument distributed to the subject of the study.

RELIABILITY OF INSTRUMENTS

Cronbach's Alpha Value for the questionnaire was (87.5%) which is appropriate for the purposes of the study.

PROCEDURES OF THE STUDY

The study carried out in the following manner:

1. The relevant literature reviewed to establish the theoretical background of the study.
2. The population identified and the samples selected on which the instruments applied.
3. The questions of the study put up, depending on previous studies.
4. The reliability and validity of the instruments approved.
5. The researcher distributed the instruments on students.
6. The instrument distributed and gathered in the Second semester of the scholastic year 2022-2023.

7. The data was gathered and analyzed by using SPSS program.
8. The researcher explained the information to reveal whether the outcomes agree or disagree with previous studies.

VARIABLES OF THE STUDY:

1. **Independent variables:** Gender (Female/Male), Academic qualification (Bachelor/ Master/ PhD), Years of experience (Less than 5 years/5-10 years/ More than 10 years)
2. **Dependent variables:**The Aspects of Administrative Creativity in Leadership Performance of PTUK.

DATA ANALYSIS

In order to analyze the data, the researchers used statistical Package for social science (SPSS), descriptive statistics (means, frequencies, percentage, and Std. Deviation) and inferential statistics. (Independent T-test, one-way ANOVA, LSD and Cronbach Alpha).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To determine The Aspects of Administrative Creativity in Leadership Performance of PTUK, and in order to interpret the results, the following arithmetic means and percentages were adopted:

An arithmetic means of (1.8–2.59) or (36–51.9%) indicates a low score.

The mean (2.60 – 3.39) or (52 – 67.9 %) indicates a Moderate score.

An arithmetic means of (3.40 – 4.19) or (68 – 83.9%) indicates a high degree.

RESULTS RELATED TO THE FIRST QUESTION

What are the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch?

To answer this question, the researcher calculated the arithmetic averages of the study sample members' estimates of the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch for each paragraph of the tool and for the total score, and Table (2) shows that.

TABLE (2): MEANS, STD. DEV. AND DEGREES OF THE ITEMS OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE.

#	Item	Mean	Degree
1	The university promotes technical education in the Palestinian society.	4	High
16	The education system at the university supports your decision to choose technical education.	3.98	High
2	Technical education curricula focus on developing the skills needed for employment.	3.97	High
6	The administration at the university plays a fruitful role in encouraging technical education.	3.91	High
11	In your opinion, the quality of technical education curricula at the university is appropriate.	3.89	High
12	The goals of technical education achieved through the university's practices.	3.87	High
3	Lecturers have the skills to teach you well.	3.86	High
4	Technical education develops skills required for the labor market.	3.86	High
5	There is a balance between theory and practice in technical education.	3.85	High
13	Suitable laboratories are available at the university.	3.83	High
7	Sufficient materials are available for practical application in laboratories.	3.82	High
14	A first aid box is available in the laboratories.	3.82	High
15	Computer and internet are available at the university.	3.8	High
8	Student visits to community institutions are good for the teaching and learning process.	3.79	High
9	The university assists its students in employment.	3.77	High
10	Field tours arranged for students.	3.77	High
17	Technical education in society linked to the needs of the labor market.	3.69	High
18	Technical education helps reduce underemployment.	3.67	High
19	Technical education is the production of skilled labor.	3.66	High
	Total	3.82	High

Results in table (2) show that the reality of the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, Ramallah Branch came to a high degree, with a mean of (3.82) over/out of (5), The paragraph "looks at educational issues from multiple angles" came in first place with an arithmetic mean (4.00) and a high degree, followed by the paragraph "seeks to overcome obstacles that hinder the achievement of goals by various possible means" with an arithmetic mean (3.98) and a high degree, followed by the paragraph "has the ability to make important decisions and bear responsibility for them" with an arithmetic mean (3.97) and a high degree, while the paragraph "gives specific objective judgments in technical and administrative topics" came in last place with an arithmetic mean (3.66) and a high degree, preceded by the paragraph "can develop the professional growth of employees" with an arithmetic mean (3.67) and a high degree, and before it the paragraph "presents the largest possible number of new ideas to develop administrative performance" with an arithmetic mean (3.69) and a high degree. This indicates that the reality of administrative creativity is available to a large extent in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, Ramallah Branch.

RESULTS RELATED TO THE SECOND QUESTION:

Is there a difference in manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch due to gender, Academic degree, and years of experience?

To answer this question, the researchers investigated the following hypothesis:

Results related to the first Hypothesis:

There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) with manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch due to gender.

To test this hypothesis, the researcher used independent t-test as table (3) shows: The results of independent t-test for the differences in participant's responses related to manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch, due to gender.

TABLE (3): RESULTS OF THE INDEPENDENT T-TEST FOR GENDER VARIABLE.

gender	Mean	Std. Error Mean	Sig.
male	4.01	0.46	0.64
female	3.98		

The results in table (3) show that the level of significance for the differences in participant's responses related to manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch, due to gender is (0.64) this means that there are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha < 0.05$), Thus, the hypothesis is accepted.

Results related to the second Hypothesis:

There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) with manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch due to Academic degree.

To test this hypothesis, the researcher used one-way ANOVA- test, table (4) shows: The results of one-way ANOVA- test for the differences in participant's responses related to manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch, due to Academic degree.

TABLE (4): THE RESULTS OF ANOVA- TEST FOR THE DIFFERENCES IN THE PARTICIPANT'S RESPONSES RELATED TO MANIFESTATIONS OF ADMINISTRATIVE CREATIVITY IN THE PERFORMANCE OF THE MANAGEMENT OF PALESTINE TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY - KHADOURI, RAMALLAH BRANCH DUE TO ACADEMIC DEGREE.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.189	2	0.094	0.33	0.72
Within Groups	130.520	47	0.287		
Total	130.709	49			

The results in this table (4) show that the level of significance for the differences in the participant's responses related to manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch, due to place of residence is (0.72) this means that there are no statistically significance differences at ($\alpha < 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis accepted.

Results related to the third Hypothesis:

There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) with manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch due to years of experience.

To test this hypothesis, the researchers used one-way ANOVA- test, table (5) shows: The results of one-way ANOVA- test for the differences in participant's responses related to manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch due to years of experience.

TABLE (5): THE RESULTS OF ANOVA- TEST FOR THE DIFFERENCES IN THE PARTICIPANT'S RESPONSES RELATED TO MANIFESTATIONS OF ADMINISTRATIVE CREATIVITY IN THE PERFORMANCE OF THE MANAGEMENT OF PALESTINE TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY - KHADOURI, RAMALLAH BRANCH DUE TO YEARS OF EXPERIENCE.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.453	2	1.226	4.351	0.13
Within Groups	128.256	47	0.282		
Total	130.709	49			

The results in this table (5) show that the level of significance for the differences in the participant's responses related to manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the management of Palestine Technical University - Khadouri, Ramallah Branch due to years of experience is (0.13) this means that there are no statistically significance differences at ($\alpha < 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis accepted.

Conclusion

The study results showed that the reality of the manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, Ramallah Branch came to a high degree, with a mean of (3.82) over/out of (5). The result also revealed that there were no statistically significant differences in due to gender, Academic degree, and years of experience.

Dissection of the results of the study

The researchers attributed The Highmanifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, Ramallah Branch to the following: Creativity is evident in the management of Palestine University through new ideas in its field of work, in developing academic specializations and programs, and in leading work teams. This is evident in every idea or procedure that is characterized by innovation and addition, and brings administrative, economic, or social benefits to the institution, individuals, or society. Therefore, the management of Palestine Technical University is not characterized by creativity, but rather it goes beyond that to be an incubator for creativity through its selection of employees who possess the characteristics of creativity and innovation, with regard to work procedures and inventing new specializations and unique work methods to accomplish the university's work, which helps it quickly adapt to conditions, which increases its effectiveness towards society from a standpoint of social responsibility by contributing to the creation of creative cadres.

The researchers attributed that there are no statistically significant differences with manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, Ramallah Branch due to gender, to the following: the ability of employees of both genders to judge the performance of the university administration, whether it is characterized by creative aspects or not, as a specific gender is not required to perceive these aspects in terms of their presence or absence.

The researchers attributed that there are are statistically significant differences with manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, Ramallah Branch due to Academic degree, to the following: It provides the ability to judge the nature of the university's management in terms of whether it reflects aspects of creativity in its performance or not. The employee does not have to have a high academic qualification to be able to realize that.

The researchers attributed that there are no statistically significant differences with manifestations of administrative creativity in the performance of the administration of Palestine Technical University - Kadoorie, Ramallah Branch due to years of experience to the following: The ability of employees of different categories and years of experience to judge the performance of the branch management in terms of its ability to be creative in performance or not, as manifestations of creativity do not require long experience to be realized.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The current study has the following limitations:

1. This population study consisted of Palestine technical university employees.
2. The study carried out in the academic year (2021-2022) at the second semester.
3. The study was limited by the concepts and definitions mentioned in it.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the results, the researchers recommended the following:

1. Encouraging employees to generate new ideas that contribute to achieving survival and growth, by focusing on practical aspects leading to achieving the best financial return and the best service alike.
2. Increasing interest in the strength of the experience of managers and benefiting their employees from the harvest of their work so that they are able to confront problems and develop appropriate solutions and encourage their employees to generate new ideas and implement change to solve problems and propose strategic solutions by holding periodic meetings that lead to building strong relationships between managers and their employees.
3. Increasing interest in the strength of rewards, and providing rewards of all kinds to their creative and distinguished employees in order to encourage them to generate new ideas and implement appropriate change that

leads to solving problems and thus facing the era with its crises and challenges, by holding celebrations during which the creative ones among them are honored.

4. Emphasizing the importance and role of human resources development as one of the strategies that can be adopted in the field of improving the performance of human resources working in it.
5. Enhancing the role of the culture of distinction, renewal and creativity for what is reflected in the performance of human resources.
6. Attention to achieving customer satisfaction to achieve a larger market share compared to other universities.

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